

Causes that generate social debt in agile software development teams

Table 1: Causes that generate social debt in agiles teams.

Id	Cause and Primary studies
Factor: Communication	
CMA1	Excessive dependence on constant interaction between team members [PS2, PS6, PS21, PS44].
CMA2	Predominant use of informal communication, as in the “architecting by osmosis” pattern [PS3, PS21].
CMA3	Lack of effective feedback between team members [PS1, PS21].
CMA4	Lack of clear communication practices between teams [PS38, PS24].
Factor: Collaboration and Social Structure	
CMA5	Limitations in remote inclusion and the construction of a shared vision [PS10, PS21, PS22, PS23, PS24, PS25].
CMA6	Distributed location of equipment affecting cohesion [PS12, PS22, PS24, PS39].
CMA7	Collaboration difficulties in hybrid or distributed environments [PS6, PS10, PS21, PS22, PS24, PS25, PS32, PS39, PS20].
CMA8	Exclusion of team members in key processes [PS1, PS21, PS22].
CMA9	Lack of team participation in technical decisions [PS1, PS10, PS22].
CMA10	Conflicts between traditional hierarchical structures and agile practices [PS21, PS22, PS39].
CMA11	Lack of or poor quality documentation [PS1, PS22, PS4].
CMA12	Presence of negative patterns such as “Newbie Free-riding” and “Cookbook Development” [PS5, PS22].
CMA13	Influence of the methodological context on team cohesion and social capital [PS9, PS12, PS21, PS22, PS23, PS32].
CMA14	Smell: Newbie Free-riding – New members receive no orientation and rely on veterans [PS5, PS22].
CMA15	Smell: Power Distance – Perception of power gaps between team members [PS5, PS22, PS24].
CMA16	Smell: Priggish Members – Excessive and uncooperative demand for compliance [PS5, PS23].
CMA17	Report-oriented meetings rather than collaborative problem solving [PS21].
Factor: Coordination	
CMA18	Inadequate management of frequent interactions [PS1, PS21].
CMA19	Ambiguity in the assignment of responsibilities [PS1, PS21].
CMA20	Lack of adherence to common standards for collaboration or version control [PS9].
CMA21	Agile scaling without adequate organizational coordination [PS21,PS39, PS45].
CMA22	Inadequate management of sprints, meetings, code reviews, or incremental deliveries [PS1, PS21, PS3].
CMA23	Lack of structural support in the scaling of agile practices [PS21, PS44, PS45].
CMA24	High autonomy without clear mechanisms for shared coordination [PS9].
CMA25	Lack of coordination in the development of shared components [PS9].

Id	Cause and Primary studies
Factor: Socio-technical Congruence	
CMA26	Distributed architecture decisions or use of offshoring [PS9, PS20, PS45].
CMA27	Use of practices such as DevOps to mitigate problems such as disengagement [PS8].
Factor: Cultural and Organizational Factors	
CMA28	High personnel turnover and loss of tacit knowledge [PS1, PS24].
CMA29	Assignment of leaders without adequate experience [PS1, PS21].
CMA30	Negative emotional impact of organizational decisions (trade-offs) [PS17, PS25].
CMA31	Pressure to deliver value quickly leading to suboptimal practices [PS26, PS43].
CMA32	Deficient or conflicting implementation of agile practices [PS1, PS21, PS39].
CMA33	Superficial or incorrect application of agile methodologies (Scrum, etc.) [PS5, PS21, PS43].
CMA34	Limited capacity of agile methods to mitigate social debt [PS5, PS9, PS12].
CMA35	Increased visibility and criticality of social debt in large-scale agile frameworks [PS21, PS44].
CMA36	Minimal differences between agile approaches (Scrum vs. others) with respect to SD generation [PS5].
CMA37	Smell: Cookbook Development – Resistance to methodological change and operational rigidity [PS9, PS5].
CMA38	Smell: Disengagement – Premature product delivery due to disinterest or disengagement [PS5, PS26].

Acronyms used: Case agile framework (CMA). Paper study (PS).